

Multiple-arrival $M/D/1$ Queue and Pandemics

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Abstract

It is important to predict the temporal dynamics of a hospital pandemic system (e.g. COVID-19). For deriving the probability of the number of patients in the hospital system, this paper uses a Theoretical $M/D/1$ queue to represent the stream of patients requiring hospitalization. It is assumed that the service (treatment period) required by each admitted patient is an equal service time D ; and the arrival rate of the new patients is Poisson λ . We give the solution to a corresponding level-crossing integral equation, which shows that the probability of $\leq n$ patients being in the system is equal to the stationary cumulative distribution function (c.d.f.- $M/D/1$) of the virtual waiting time at time nD . We use this equality to approximate the number of patients in the hospital system over a time interval. Finally, the paper presents the “temporal dynamics” of a real-world COVID-19 pandemic example in Ontario, Canada during 2020-2021.

Key words: Stochastic model, stochastic level crossings, $M/D/1$ queue, stationary probability cumulative distribution function, pandemic, temporal dynamics. virtual waiting time.

1. Introduction

It is important to be able to predict or estimate the temporal dynamics of a pandemic, such as the recently-occurred real-world COVID-19 pandemic between April 19, 2020 and June 30, 2021 in Ontario, Canada. This can help hospitals, medical clinics, and medical practitioners prepare for a newly expected pandemic. We consider first a Theoretically active pandemic (like but not identical to, COVID-19.) The goal of this study is to test whether we can predict or estimate the temporal dynamics on the host population of real-world COVID 19, by using a unique property of the $M/D/1$ queue to represent the stream of patients requiring hospitalization; namely that the service (treatment period) required by each admitted patient is an equal service time D ; and the arrival rate of the new patients is Poisson λ . We give the solution to the corresponding level-crossing integral equation. It shows that the probability of $N \leq n$ patients in the system is equal to the stationary cumulative distribution function (c.d.f.) of the actual waiting time at time nD .

Thus, every patient in the theoretical system gets the same service time D . This property may make the temporal dynamics of Pandemic resemble approximately the temporal dynamics of real-world COVID-19 (see Figure 4 in Section 5, the temporal dynamics of the real-world COVID-19 pandemic which appears in Huang, et.al. (2023), Government of Canada (2021) and Government of Ontario (2021)).

Figure 1. The Stationary p.d.f. and c.d.f. of virtual Wait of M/D/1 queue

1.1. Brief Literature Review

Deriving the stationary p.d.f. of a key random variable (r.v.) in a stochastic model is an important problem. Several classical authors have researched the topic, e.g., Lindley (1952); Cox (1962), Feller (1966) and others. Recent authors have researched the topic, e.g., Brill [1975, 2014, 2017, 2023]; Harris, Brill and Fischer (2000); and others, using the System Point Level Crossing method which is a simple rate-balance technique. An example of the stationary pdf of the virtual wait in an M/D/1 queue is given, along with explanation, in Section 3.4.4, pp. 85-88, including Figure 3.5 on p. 87, in the reference Brill (2023).

1.2. The purpose of this paper

We noticed that the shape of the stationary p.d.f. of the virtual wait in a standard M/D/1 queue roughly resembles increase in symptoms for new individual infections in the pattern of the temporal dynamics of the real-world epidemic COVID-19 data in Ontario, Canada in Figure 4 in Section 5 below.

This paper utilizes the following approach to obtain Formula (12) below:

$$\text{Prob}(N \leq n \text{ patients in system}) = F(nD).$$

which shows that the probability of $N \leq n$ patients being in the system is equal to the stationary cumulative distribution function (c.d.f.-M/D/1) of the virtual waiting time at time nD . We use this equality to approximate the number of patients in the hospital system over a time interval.

Section 2 discusses the theory of the level crossing estimation method; the analytic solutions of the p.d.f. and c.d.f. of waiting time for the M/D/1 queue is given in Section 3. We discuss the probability of number in system in Section 4. In Section 5, we view a real-world example of COVID-19 by using the M/D/1 queue approach. Finally, the summary of the paper is given in Section 6.

2. Theory of Level-Crossing Estimation Method

Previously proved, simple limit theorems show that the sample-path down-crossing rate of an arbitrary fixed state-space level, say $x > 0$, is equal to a simple mathematical function of the analytic stationary probability density function (p.d.f.) of the key random variable (Chapter 2 in Brill, Ph.D. Dissertation, 1975). We illustrate the technique using an example of estimating the stationary p.d.f. of the virtual wait in a variate of the M/D/1 queue, below. Similar level-crossing estimation (LCE) methods apply to: the virtual wait in M/G/1 queues; the virtual wait in G/M/1 queues; the virtual wait in M/M/c queues; the net inventory in inventory systems; the buffer size in actuarial ruin models; the serum concentration of a prescription drug in multiple dosing pharmaceutical models; the effect on people of multiple ads in advertising, etc. (see Brill, 2023.)

2.1. Level-Crossing Theorem

Definition 1: $\mathcal{D}_t(x)$ = the number of SP (System Point, leading point of sample path thought of dynamically over time) “down-crossings” of level $x > 0$ during time interval $[0, t]$.

Definition 2: $\mathcal{U}_t(x)$ = the number of SP “up-crossings” of level $x > 0$ during time interval $[0, t]$.

Definition 3. \mathcal{I}_t = the number of SP impacts (SP hits of level-zero from above during time interval $[0, t]$).

Remark: $\{ \mathcal{D}_t(x) \}$, $\{ \mathcal{U}_t(x) \}$ and $\{ \mathcal{I}_t \}$ are counting processes and their sample paths are “non-decreasing step functions on time interval $[0, t]$ ”. Due to Poisson arrivals, $\{ \mathcal{D}_t(x) \}$, $x > 0$ and $\{ \mathcal{I}_t \}$ are delayed renewal processes (first inter-renewal differs from remaining inter-renewals).

We use here an M/D/1 queue as an example to define the stationary p.d.f. and c.d.f. of virtual waiting time in stochastic models.

Definition 4: $f(x)$, $x > 0$, is the stationary p.d.f. of the virtual wait $W(t)$; $f(x)$ is also the stationary p.d.f. of the actual wait, due to the PASTA principle (Poisson Arrivals See Time Averages); P_0 is $P(\text{wait} = 0)$.

Theorem 1. (PH, Brill, 1974, Ph.D. thesis) For the M/D/1 queue, the steady-state stationary p.d.f. of virtual wait $\{W(t)\}_{t>0}$

(1) $\{P_0, f(x)\}_{x>0}$ has exactly one atom, which is at $x = 0$;

(2) $f(x)$ has a downward jump discontinuity of size λP_0 at $x = D$;

(3) $f(x)$ is continuous for all $x > 0$, $x \neq D$.

Remark.

1. State $\{0\}$ is an atom since a sample path spends a positive proportion of time in $\{0\}$ (a.s.), namely $P_0 = 1 - \lambda D > 0$. The state space $S = [0, \infty]$ has no other atoms, since the proportion of time the SP spends in each state $x > 0$ is 0.

2. Consider state-space levels D and $D - \varepsilon$, $0 < \varepsilon < D$, fix time $t > 0$. $T_t^b(D)$ is the number of tangents of level D from below during $(0, t)$.

Figure 2. Sample path of virtual wait $\{W(t)\}_{t>0}$ for $M/D/1$ queue. Black circles at peaks indicate right continuity. In this figure, there are 3 tangents from below at level D .

Figure 3. Sample path of virtual wait $\{W(t)\}_{t>0}$ for $M/D/1$ queue showing levels D and $D - \varepsilon$ and instants $t, t + \varepsilon$, where ε is small.

We have

$$\mathcal{D}_{t+\varepsilon}(D - \varepsilon) = \sum_{j=1}^{\mathcal{D}_t(D) + T_t^b(D)} I_j(D, \varepsilon), \quad (1)$$

here $I_j(\chi, \varepsilon) = 1$ if the j^{th} down-crossing or tangent of level χ from below, is followed by a down-crossing of level $\chi - \varepsilon$ exactly ε time units later, and $I_j(\chi, \varepsilon) = 0$ otherwise.

Due to the memoryless property of exponential probability distribution

$$P\{I_j(\chi, \varepsilon) = 1\} = e^{-\lambda\varepsilon}, \chi > 0. \quad (2)$$

Set

$$\chi = D; I_j(D, \varepsilon) \text{ is independent of } \mathcal{D}_t(D) + T_t^b(D), E[I_j(D, \varepsilon)] = e^{-\lambda\varepsilon}, j = 1, 2, \dots$$

Then we take expected value, on both sides of (5) gives

$$E[\mathcal{D}_{t+\varepsilon}(D - \varepsilon)] = E[\mathcal{D}_t(D) + T_t^b(D)]e^{-\lambda\varepsilon}, \quad (3)$$

Therefore

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{E[\mathcal{D}_t(D)]}{t} = f(D), \text{ and } \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{E[\mathcal{D}_t(D - \varepsilon)]}{t} = f(D - \varepsilon). \quad (4)$$

2.2. Principle of Rate Balance for Level x in State Space

Corollary 1. *By the elementary Renewal Theorem,*

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{E[\mathcal{D}_t(D)]}{t} = f(D), x > 0, \quad (5)$$

and

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathcal{D}_t(D)}{t} \underset{a.s.}{=} f(D), x > 0, \quad (6)$$

where, “ $=$ ” means “equal almost surely” or “with probability 1”.

Above formulas (5) and (6) mean that for each x in the state space, the (long run) SP down-crossing and up-crossing rates of level x are equal; we have

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{E[\mathcal{D}_t(x)]}{t} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{E[\mathcal{U}_t(x)]}{t} = \lambda P_0 \bar{B}(x) + \lambda \int_{y=0}^x \bar{B}(x-y) f(y) dy, x > 0,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathcal{D}_t(x)}{t} \underset{a.s.}{=} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathcal{U}_t(x)}{t} = \lambda P_0 \bar{B}(x) + \lambda \int_{y=0}^x \bar{B}(x-y) f(y) dy, x > 0.$$

Notation:

$F(x) = P(W(t) \leq x)$ is the stationary c.d.f. of virtual wait at level $x, x \geq 0$.

$P_0 = F(0)$.

$B(y) = P(S \leq y)$ is the c.d.f. of the service time at level $y, y \geq 0$.

$\bar{B}(y) = 1 - B(y), y \geq 0$, used to get (8) from (7), below.

2.3. Level Crossing Integral Equation

By Theorem 1 and Corollary 1, we write a “*rate-balance*” equation which is an integral equation (7).

$f(x)$	$=$	$\lambda \bar{B}(x) P_0$	$+$	$\lambda \int_{y=0}^x \bar{B}(x-y) f(y) dy$	(7)
↓		↓		↓	
Downcrossing		Upcrossing		Upcrossing	
Rate of level x		Rate from		Rate from	
		level $x=0$		levels in $(0, x)$	

This “*rate balance*” technique (discovered in Brill, 1974, Ph.D. Thesis) avoids a great deal of time-consuming algebraic steps previously required by starting directly with a Lindley recursion, ending with the same integral equation (7). For more explanation of sample paths, see Cramer & Leadbetter (1967).

2.4. Summary of Steps of Derivation and Finding Solution of Level-Crossing Integral Equation

1. Construct a sample path of the virtual waiting time, $\{W(t)\}_{t \geq 0}$.
2. Substitute from (2) and (4) term by term into (6).
3. Write integral equation (7) immediately by observing the sample path down-and up-crossings.
4. Find solution of the p.d.f. $f(x)$ in integral equation (7).

Note: The derivation of (7) for p.d.f. $f(x)$, $x > 0$, can be obtained by a sequence of algebraic steps, but it is a long process which needs long computational time (hours, days or weeks depending on complexity). This motivates us to develop a useful estimation method using the “System Point Level Crossing Technique” (Brill, 1975).

3. Analytic Solution for c.d.f. and p.d.f. of wait of M/D/1 Queue

Apply the alternative solution for M/D/1 queue of basic LC equation (7) with

$$B(x-y) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x-y < D; \\ 1, & \text{if } x-y \geq D. \end{cases}$$

We have the solutions for c.d.f. and p.d.f. of wait of M/D/1 queue in equation (8):

$f(x)$	$=$	$\lambda F(x)$	$-$	$\lambda F(x-D)$	(8)
↓		↓		↓	
Downcrossing		Upcrossing		Upcrossing	
Rate of level x		Rate from		Rate from	
		start set $[0, x]$		start set $[0, x-D)$	

In formula (8) the left side $f(x)$ is the down-crossing rate of level x . On right side of (8), the first term is up-crossing rate of level x from all states in $[0, x]$; the second term subtracts off the number of up-crossings from all states in $[0, x - D]$. We can get analytic solution for the c.d.f. and p.d.f. as follows.

(1) **CDF of Wait:**

$$F(x) = P_0 \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor x/D \rfloor} (-\lambda)^i \frac{(x-iD)^i}{i!} e^{\lambda(x-iD)}, \quad x \geq 0; \quad (9)$$

Where $\lfloor \alpha \rfloor :=$ greatest interger ≤ 0 .

(2) **PDF of Wait:**

Case 1: by differentiating $F(x)$ in (9), we have

$$f(x) = \lambda P_0 e^{\lambda x}, \quad 0 < x < D. \quad (10)$$

Case 2: for $x \in [mD, (m+1)D]$, $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, with respect to x , we have

$$f(x) = \lambda P_0 \sum_{i=0}^m (-\lambda)^i \frac{(x-iD)^i}{i!} e^{\lambda(x-iD)} - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} (-\lambda)^i \frac{(x-(i+1)D)^i}{i!} e^{\lambda(x-(i+1)D)}. \quad (11)$$

4. Probability Distribution of Number in System

Let N be the number of customers (patients) in the system at an arbitrary time point.

Let $W_q (\geq 0)$ be the wait before the service, in the steady-state.

Let $P_n := P(N = n)$, be the number of customers in the system.

Assume Poinson arrivals, $a_n = P_n = d_n$, $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$, Then arrivals "see" n customers in the system if

$$W_q \geq 0 \text{ and } W_q \in [(n-1)D, nD], \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Thus

$$a_n = F(nD) - F((n-1)D) = P_n = d_n, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

From (9) we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_0 &= F(0) - F(-D) = F(0) = P_0; \\ P_1 &= F(D) - F(0) = P_0 e^{\lambda D} - P_0 (e^{\lambda D} - 1); \\ P_2 &= F(2D) - F(D) = P_0 e^{\lambda D} (-\lambda D + e^{\lambda D} - 1) \\ &\dots\dots \\ P_n &= F(nD) - F((n-1)D), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

The c.d.f. of N is

$$P(N \leq n) = \sum_{i=1}^n P_i = F(nD), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad (12)$$

where $F(nD)$ is computed using (9).

5. A COVID-19 Example in Ontario, Canada

Figures 1(a) and 1(b) refer to a single cycle of a new pandemic. In Figure 4, the time period includes 3 successive cycles of a real-world pandemic. We compare the patterns of the temporal dynamics of pandemic-T (from using M/D/1 queue) with the temporal dynamics of a real-world COVID-19.

The real-world COVID-19 virus we use for comparison was confirmed in Canada on January 27, 2020, and in March 2020. As cases of community transmission were confirmed, all of Canada's provinces and territories declared states of emergency. Provinces and territories implemented, to varying degrees, school and daycare closures, prohibitions on gatherings, closures of non-essential businesses and restrictions on entry. By mid to late summer of 2020, Canada saw a steady decline in active cases of COVID until late summer. Through autumn of 2020, the country saw a resurgence of cases in all provinces and territories (Government of Canada, 2021). The province of Ontario Canada, in late summer of 2021, began preparing for a fourth wave of the virus, which was largely affecting unvaccinated individuals. In January 2022, there were changes in the policy regarding testing, such that the reported number of new positive cases no longer reflects the true number of new positive cases. In this paper, we focus on data from April 19, 2020-June 30, 2021, Ontario COVID-19 cases daily data collected for $n^* = 438$ days (Government of Ontario (2021)). We focus on high numbers of hospitalized COVID-19 patient's relationship with percent positive tests last day and the number of new cases. Percent positive tests last day is the percent of COVID-19 tests that were positive in the last day. The response variable is the number of hospitalized COVID-19 patients. To focus on high numbers of hospitalized COVID-19 patients, its upper quartile (75%) 1010, will be used as a threshold. After applying the threshold of 1010, the data was reduced to $n = 103$ days. Figure 4 is a chart plot showing $n^* = 438$ days of hospitalized COVID-19 patients.

Figure 4. In Ontario Canada, the number of hospitalized COVID-19 patients in 438 days ($n^* = 438$) between April 19, 2020, and June 30, 2021, with a threshold of 1010 hospitalized COVID-19 patients. The number of days with data value above 1010 threshold is 103 days ($n = 103$).

In Figure 4, we also note that there were three waves of COVID-19 during April 19, 2020 – June 30, 2021. The top three values are 1043 patients on May-04-2020, 1674 patients on Jan-13-2021, and 2360 patients on April 20, 2021. Our goal at that time was to create a statistical model to analyze the current Ontario hospitalized COVID-19 patients' number and predict future extreme events. (Huang, et al, 2023). Please see Figure 4 of Ontario, Canada COVID-19 Patients in Hospital daily.

Table 1. Number of COVID-19 patients in Ontario Hospital System

History Peak COVID-19 patients in Ontario hospital system	Predict the number N of COVID-19 patients in Ontario hospital system in the future	With Probability
2360 (April, 2021)	Prob(N <=2360)	57.16%
1674 (January, 2021)	Prob(N <= 1674)	52.57%
1043 (May, 2020)	Prob(N <=1043)	47,50%

Main Steps Using M/D/1 Queue to Analyze Pandemic Example

Step 1. The pattern of the stationary p.d.f. of the virtual wait in an M/D/1 queue rises immediately in a slightly convex curve to a finite peak. Then the p.d.f. immediately drops vertically to a positive level. The pdf then decreases in continuous upper-half loops, further toward level 0. The p.d.f. then declines smoothly to level 0 over time (see Figure 1(a)). This M/D/1 property is analogous to the development of individual’s symptoms. (See Section 3.4.4, on pp. 85-88 in Brill 2023, *Introduction to Stochastic Level Crossing Techniques*, CRC Press.)

Step 2. We reach a formula for M/D/1 queue developed originally by A.K. Erlang (1909) which relates the c.d.f. of the number of customers in the queueing system and the sample path of the actual wait at customer arrival times. (in COVID-19 example in this paper, the customers are the patients in the hospital system). See Table 1 above.

Step 3. Given a formula for the c.d.f. of the number of customers in the system, we can plot the number of queuing customers in a graph over time.

Step 4. We can then compare the plot of number of M/D/1 customers over time with the real data about the number of infections over time of the real-world COVID-19 pandemic.

Step 5. We can develop a measure of the discrepancy between the M/D/1 pattern say, $\hat{g}(x)$ and the real-world pattern $g(x)$ values, by evaluating the integral:

$$\rho_{\text{Distance}} = \int_0^t |\hat{g}(x) - g(x)| dx. \tag{13}$$

6. Conclusions

Conclusion 1. The Stochastic-level crossing estimation (LCE) method is useful for estimating the stationary p.d.f. and c.d.f. of the virtual waiting time.

Conclusion 2. Investigation of stationary c.d.f. of the virtual waiting M/D/1 queue, may contribute to pandemic research. HOPEFULLY, it can obtain good estimation of the distribution of COVID-19 cases and the number of patients in the COVID-19 hospital system.

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